

UN conventions on new tax systems to narrow the gap between the world's rich and poor and reduce wars

----- Novel Strategies for Maintaining Durable Global Peace-7

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Abstract

Although the number of people receiving higher education globally has increased by at least threefold since the establishment of the Nobel Peace Prize, the frequency of economic crises and wars has not decreased. One of the core factors contributing to many of the above problems is the unreasonable tax system, which leads to the widening of the wealth gap and an increase in the potential war population. In some countries, the threshold for inheritance tax is set too low, so that some individuals are either unwilling or unable to inherit assets, and then these assets are acquired by the government or companies at a low price. The unreasonable tax rates of personal income tax and inheritance tax have led the rich to adopt strategies such as immigration or various tax avoidance means. There is even a situation where the personal income tax rate of the wealthy is lower than that of the middle class. Charity funds have largely become tax avoidance tools for the wealthy to transfer private assets. This is not only not conducive to narrowing the wealth gap, but on the contrary, it promotes the further concentration of wealth to the super-rich, further increases social inequality, and is extremely unfavorable to national consumption growth. The super-rich are also prone to interfere in the country's political and economic operations. Therefore, any funds or assets donated to a charitable foundation should be fully used for assistance purposes within five to six years. The international community and the United Nations should formulate reasonable systems for relevant issues and reach a global consensus, and at the same time revise the constitutions of various countries. The author firmly believes that once this new tax system can achieve global reform, it can be regarded as a revolutionary change and a major innovation in reducing wars from the perspective of war behavior economics or military behavior economics, and it will bring a new milestone-like future for maintaining global peace and sustainable development.

Keywords: personal income tax · personal income tax rates · inheritance tax · inheritance tax rates · gift tax rates · tax system · tax evasion · regional economy · economic crisis · US treasury bonds · government behavioral economics · national governance · global governance · governmental consensus · charitable foundation · trust fund · governmental ethics · war behavior economics · military behavior economics

1. An unreasonable tax system is a significant cause of widening wealth disparity, economic or financial crises, and even wars.

Despite efforts to promote world peace through initiatives such as the Nobel Peace Prize and increased education levels among politicians, wars continued to occur. This is because influential politicians and funders with higher education have greater power than peace advocates. Economic and financial crises contribute significantly to wars. The main reasons include governments deliberately creating poverty to increase the likelihood of war, countries with low inheritance tax thresholds leading to government acquisition of property at a low price, wealthy individuals evading taxes by migrating to smaller countries, and wealth concentration due to inadequate taxation of substantial assets. The high personal income tax rate has led the wealthy to seek tax avoidance. Additionally, unreasonable inheritance and income tax systems fail to effectively regulate the wealth gap, resulting in continuous tax avoidance by the wealthy and a concentration of wealth in the hands of a few individuals. Despite the global increase in money supply, there is still insufficient currency in circulation. This distorted social perception prioritizes money and material possessions, perpetuating the accumulation of wealth by the affluent class, and hindering the establishment of a globally harmonious society based on kindness, productivity, civility, and morality. This situation increases the likelihood of social conflicts, tensions, and wars.

From the perspective of historical lessons, in the late years of the prosperous Tang Dynasty in China, wealth was highly concentrated among officials and plutocrats. However, in 874¹, successive years of floods and droughts occurred throughout the country. There was almost no harvest of autumn crops, and the victims were unable to receive relief. As a result, peasant uprisings broke out. Among them, the Huang Chao uprising army **killed a total of about eight million officials and plutocrats**, etc., changing China's class structure².

Table 1. Several typical data on global wealth concentration

In 2019, global wealth reached \$361 trillion, with the top 1% owning 44% of total wealth ³ .
By 2021, the wealthiest 10% of the global population controlled 76% of the world's wealth. In contrast, the bottom 50% only possessed 2% of the wealth. Meanwhile, the middle 40% held 22% of the wealth ⁴ .
The richest 10% of Indians own 77% of the country's wealth. In 2017, the wealthiest 1% received 73% of the wealth, while the poorest half of the Indian population saw their wealth grow by only 1% ⁵ .
By 2020, around 500 Russian billionaires controlled more wealth than the poorest 99.8% of Russians, with 40% of household wealth held by the financial elite ⁶ .
In the U.S. , the richest 10% hold 69.8% of total net worth, with the top 1% owning half of the wealth and the following 9% owning the other half. The bottom 50% of Americans own just 2% of the total wealth ⁷ .
In China , the top 10% of the population's share of national income increased from 27% in 1978 to 41% in 2015, while the share of the bottom 50% decreased from 27% to 15%. However, wealth is more concentrated than income, as the top 10% own 67%

of wealth compared to 41% of income. The wealthiest 0.0001% of Chinese individuals own 5.8% of total wealth, roughly equivalent to the bottom 50%⁸.

In addition, the Matthew Effect indirectly verifies the effectiveness of the Pareto Principle^{9,10}, as the poor become increasingly impoverished and the rich become even wealthier, resulting in wealth concentration in the top 20% of the population. Conversely, the Pareto Principle also validates the existence of the Matthew Effect, as the top 20% of wealthy individuals have greater opportunities to acquire resources and accumulate funds at a faster pace, leading to the perpetuation of this wealth inequality where the rich get even richer and the poor get even poorer. However, the government actions in many countries lag behind the changes in the free market, and the absence of negative feedback regulatory mechanisms means they have been unable to effectively control the Matthew Effect and the Pareto Principle in economic operations. As a result, the balancing of wealth inequality and the reduction of economic crises has not been achieved. The Matthew effect and the Pareto principle mutually confirm each other, highlighting the necessity of implementing global changes in systems such as personal income tax and inheritance tax.

2. Personal income tax rates

At present, personal income tax rates in some countries can be as high as 35-56%¹¹, which is excessively high and highly unreasonable. It severely lacks basic respect for individuals who legally create wealth and inevitably leads to widespread legal tax evasion by the wealthy. They can either transfer their assets to fake charitable foundations, trusts, or other means to avoid taxes. In fact, more and more people are giving up their American citizenship to avoid taxes¹². According to ProPublica, from 2014 to 2018, the total wealth of the 25 richest Americans increased by \$401 billion. However, data from the U.S. Internal Revenue Service (IRS) reveals that over the five years, despite paying a total of \$13.6 billion in personal income taxes, their effective tax rate was only 3.4%. In these years, the median annual income of American households is approximately \$70,000, and they pay a 14% personal income tax rate. For couples earning more than \$628,300, the highest income tax rate is 37%¹³. On September 15, 2021, the White House released a report stating that from 2010 to 2018, the average federal individual income tax rate for the wealthiest 400 American families was 8.2%. The report mentions that this is due to the tax treatment of investment income such as capital gains and dividends. By comparison, according to analysis by the Tax Policy Center, the average income tax rate for Americans in 2018 was 13.3%¹⁴.

Clearly, the American system also does not encourage individuals with strong profitability to reinvest their funds back into society, thus hindering job creation and economic development in the United States. In fact, when private companies face financial crises, these individuals are forced to increase their personal investments, and some even end up losing everything. However, the national or local tax authorities do not refund the total amount of taxes paid by business owners in such cases, which is a situation that occurs frequently in China. The unreasonable national tax system is one of the reasons for the treasury bond crisis.

Taking various factors into account, it is recommended that for individuals with total personal assets of less than \$80 million, the maximum income tax rate on personal income should generally not exceed 25% in countries around the world. For sole proprietorship companies and limited companies, the income portion attributed to individuals shall not be subject to repeated taxation. In special countries or under special circumstances, it should not exceed 30%. For individuals with total assets in excess of \$80 million, taxes shall be paid at the rate shown in **Table 1**.

Investment profits in the secondary market should be included in personal income on an annual basis and taxed accordingly. Individuals who support family members or have special circumstances such as caring for parents or children's education should be granted sufficient tax deductions. Tax avoidance through false charitable funds should be prohibited. Moreover, personal income tax should not be paid twice. Any amount already taxed through a personal company should no longer be subject to personal income tax. By reducing tax avoidance among the wealthy, the country will actually generate more tax revenue.

Table 1. International Convention on the Personal Income Tax Rates for Rich Individuals with Extraordinary Assets

	Personal total assets	income tax rate
1	\$80 million ≤ Personal total assets < \$100 million	between 29% and 30%
2	\$100 million ≤ Personal total assets < \$300 million	between 30% and 32%
3	\$300 million ≤ Personal total assets < \$500 million	between 32% and 33%
4	\$500 million ≤ Personal total assets < \$700 million	between 32% and 33%
5	\$700 million ≤ Personal total assets < \$900 million	between 32% and 33%
6	\$900 million ≤ Personal total assets < \$1.2 billion	between 32% and 33%
7	\$1.2 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$1.5 billion	between 34% and 38%
8	\$1.5 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$1.7 billion	between 34% and 38%
9	\$1.7 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$1.9 billion	between 34% and 38%
10	\$1.9 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$2.1 billion	between 34% and 38%
11	\$2.1 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$2.5 billion	between 39% and 43%
12	\$2.5 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$3 billion	between 39% and 43%
13	\$3 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$4 billion	between 39% and 43%
14	\$4 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$5 billion	between 44% and 47%
15	\$5 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$6 billion	between 44% and 47%
16	\$6 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$7 billion	between 44% and 47%
17	\$7 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$8 billion	between 48% and 51%
18	\$9 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$10 billion	between 48% and 51%
19	\$10 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$15 billion	between 48% and 51%
20	\$15 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$20 billion	between 48% and 51%
21	\$20 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$25 billion	between 48% and 51%
22	\$25 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$30 billion	between 48% and 51%
23	\$30 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$35 billion	between 52% and 56%
24	\$35 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$40 billion	between 52% and 56%
25	\$40 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$45 billion	between 52% and 56%

26	\$45 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$50 billion	between 52% and 56%
27	\$50 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$55 billion	between 57% and 59%
28	\$55 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$60 billion	between 57% and 59%
29	\$60 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$65 billion	between 57% and 59%
30	\$65 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$70 billion	between 57% and 59%
31	\$70 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$75 billion	between 60% and 61%
32	\$75 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$80 billion	between 60% and 61%
33	\$80 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$85 billion	between 60% and 61%
34	\$85 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$90 billion	between 60% and 61%
35	\$90 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$95 billion	between 60% and 61%
36	\$95 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$1 trillion	between 60% and 61%
37	\$1 trillion ≤ Personal total assets < \$2 trillion	between 62% and 64%
38	\$2 trillion ≤ Personal total assets < \$3 trillion	between 62% and 64%
39	\$3 trillion ≤ Personal total assets < \$4 trillion	between 62% and 64%
40	\$4 trillion ≤ Personal total assets < \$5 trillion	between 62% and 64%
41	\$5 trillion ≤ Personal total assets < \$6 trillion	between 65% and 68%
42	\$6 trillion ≤ Personal total assets < \$7 trillion	between 68% and 70%
43	\$7 trillion ≤ Personal total assets < \$8 trillion	between 68% and 70%
44	\$8 trillion ≤ Personal total assets < \$9 trillion	between 68% and 70%
45	\$9 trillion ≤ Personal total assets < \$10 trillion	between 68% and 70%
46	\$10 trillion ≤ inherited estate	between 70% and 72%

3. Inheritance tax rate, nationality change tax rate and sustainable economic development and global peace

Currently, inheritance tax collection standards vary from country to country. Although inheritance tax rates in some countries range from 45% to 70%, the structure is unreasonable¹⁵. According to statistics, in 2020 alone, there were more than 60 billion yen worth of properties in Japan that were in a state of abandonment¹⁶. The excessively high maximum rates are highly unreasonable and show a serious lack of respect for those who have legally created wealth. When these legacies exist in the form of normally operating enterprises, excessive inheritance taxes will inevitably significantly damage the company's equity structure and bring great instability to the company's operations. This is not conducive to the effective management of the inherited enterprise by the inheritor. This inevitably leads to widespread tax evasion or the transfer of assets to fraudulent charitable foundations, disguising them as legitimate tax avoidance, or finding other ways to avoid taxes. These practices clearly hinder the rational distribution of social wealth and the proper circulation of money, and are detrimental to sustainable global peace. Therefore, it is necessary to establish a government consensus on the collection of global inheritance taxes.

The author believes that anyone on earth, whether they are kings, emperors, popes, or individuals with significant assets, even if they have transferred their assets to charitable foundations, should still be liable for inheritance tax based on the value of the assets if they have not been fully donated within 5 - 6 years. Otherwise, these charitable funds are not truly charitable funds. If they wish to inherit such assets, they

must pay inheritance tax. Regardless of personal wealth, the minimum tax threshold should not be less than \$10 million. The minimum taxable threshold for wealthy people with different assets should also be different (Table 2). Otherwise, heirs will try their best to evade taxes, leading to a widening wealth gap, intensifying social conflicts, and endless thirst or greed for wealth could potentially lead to war.

However, the author believes that regardless of individual wealth, the maximum tax rate for renouncing citizenship should not exceed 40% (Table 3). Wealthy individuals with different asset levels should have different minimum tax thresholds, and individuals who renounce citizenship should have basic tax exemption guarantees. The tax rate of gift tax can be adjusted based on the model of inheritance tax.

Table 2. International conventions proposing Inherited estate or Grant tax

	Inherited estate or Grant tax	Minimum threshold	Tax rate for excess portion
1	\$20 million $\leq$ inherited estate < \$40 million	\$15million	between 10% and 14%
2	\$40 million $\leq$ inherited estate < \$60 million	\$16 million	between 10% and 14%
3	\$60 million $\leq$ inherited estate < \$80 million	\$17 million	between 12% and 16%
4	\$80 million $\leq$ inherited estate < \$100 million	\$18 million	between 12% and 18%
5	\$100 million $\leq$ inherited estate < \$300 million	\$20 million	between 15% and 26%
6	\$300 million $\leq$ inherited estate < \$500 million	\$30 million	between 20% and 28%
7	\$500 million $\leq$ inherited estate < \$700 million	\$40 million	between 23% and 28%
8	\$700 million $\leq$ inherited estate < \$900 million	\$50 million	between 23% and 28%
9	\$900 million $\leq$ inherited estate < \$1.2 billion	\$60 million	between 24% and 28%
10	\$1.2 billion $\leq$ inherited estate < \$1.5 billion	\$70 million	between 25% and 28%
11	\$1.5 billion $\leq$ inherited estate < \$1.7 billion	\$80 million	between 25% and 28%
12	\$1.7 billion $\leq$ inherited estate < \$1.9 billion	\$90 million	between 25% and 28%
13	\$1.9 billion $\leq$ inherited estate < \$2.1 billion	\$100 million	between 25% and 30%
14	\$2.1 billion $\leq$ inherited estate < \$2.5 billion	\$110 million	between 28% and 32%
15	\$2.5 billion $\leq$ inherited estate < \$3 billion	\$120 million	between 28% and 32%

16	\$3 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$4 billion	\$130 million	between 28% and 32%
17	\$4 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$5 billion	\$140 million	between 35% and 38%
18	\$5 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$6 billion	\$150 million	between 35% and 38%
19	\$6 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$7 billion	\$160 million	between 35% and 38%
20	\$7 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$8 billion	\$170 million	between 35% and 38%
21	\$9 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$10 billion	\$180 million	between 40% and 45%
22	\$10 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$15 billion	\$190 million	between 40% and 45%
23	\$15 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$20 billion	\$200 million	between 50% and 55%
24	\$20 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$25 billion	\$210 million	between 50% and 55%
25	\$25 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$30 billion	\$220 million	between 55% and 60%
26	\$30 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$35 billion	\$230 million	between 55% and 60%
27	\$35 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$40 billion	\$240 million	between 55% and 60%
28	\$40 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$45 billion	\$250 million	between 55% and 60%
29	\$45 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$50 billion	\$260 million	between 55% and 60%
30	\$50 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$55 billion	\$270 million	between 55% and 60%
31	\$55 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$60 billion	\$280 million	between 55% and 60%
32	\$60 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$65 billion	\$290 million	between 55% and 60%
33	\$65 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$70 billion	\$300 million	between 55% and 60%
34	\$70 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$75 billion	\$310 million	between 55% and 60%
35	\$75 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$80 billion	\$320 million	between 55% and 60%
36	\$80 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$85 billion	\$330 million	between 55% and 60%
37	\$85 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$90 billion	\$340 million	between 55% and 60%

38	\$90 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$95 billion	\$350 million	between 55% and 60%
39	\$95 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$1 trillion	\$360 million	between 55% and 60%
40	\$1 trillion ≤ inherited estate < \$2 trillion	\$370 million	between 61% and 62%
41	\$2 trillion ≤ inherited estate < \$3 trillion	\$380 million	between 61% and 62%
42	\$3 trillion ≤ inherited estate < \$4 trillion	\$390 million	between 61% and 62%
43	\$4 trillion ≤ inherited estate < \$5 trillion	\$400 million	between 61% and 62%
44	\$5 trillion ≤ inherited estate < \$6 trillion	\$410 million	between 63% and 64%
45	\$6 trillion ≤ inherited estate < \$7 trillion	\$420 million	between 63% and 64%
46	\$7 trillion ≤ inherited estate < \$8 trillion	\$430 million	between 64% and 65%
47	\$8 trillion ≤ inherited estate < \$9 trillion	\$440 million	between 64% and 65%
48	\$9 trillion ≤ inherited estate < \$10 trillion	\$450 million	between 64% and 65%
49	\$10 trillion ≤ inherited estate	\$460 million	between 67% and 68%

Note: Prohibiting individuals or institutions from using charitable trusts or other means for tax evasion. Estate and gift tax rates should adhere to the rules outlined in Table S 2, which all countries worldwide must follow. Any country or region found aiding tax evasion will have its assets frozen FIVEfold.

The inheritance tax on museum and manufacturing assets can be reduced directly by 2 to 4 percentage points.

Grant tax rate: The maximum tax rate that the recipient of the gift should pay for all the wealth donated by a single donor within six years, except for public welfare donations.

Table 3. Suggested Tax Rate for Change of Nationality

	Nationality change tax	Minimum threshold	Tax rate for excess portion
1	\$20 million ≤ total assets < \$40 million	\$1 million	between 20% and 25%
2	\$40 million ≤ total assets < \$60 million	\$2 million	between 20% and 25%
3	\$60 million ≤ total assets < \$80 million	\$3 million	between 23% and 28%
4	\$80 million ≤ total assets < \$100 million	\$4 million	between 23% and 28%

5	\$100 million ≤total assets<\$300 million	\$5 million	between 28% and 32%
6	\$300 million ≤total assets<\$500 million	\$6 million	between 28% and 32%
7	\$500 million ≤total assets<\$700 million	\$7million	between 28% and 32%
8	\$700 million ≤total assets<\$900 million	\$8million	between 30% and 32%
9	\$900 million ≤total assets<\$1.2 billion	\$9 million	between 30% and 32%
10	\$1.2 billion≤total assets<\$1.5 billion	\$10million	between 30% and 35%
11	\$1.5 billion≤total assets<\$1.7 billion	\$11million	between 30% and 35%
12	\$1.7 billion≤total assets<\$1.9 billion	\$12million	between 30% and 35%
13	\$1.9 billion≤total assets<\$2.1 billion	\$13million	between 30% and 35%
14	\$2.1 billion≤total assets<\$2.5 billion	\$14 million	between 30% and 35%
15	\$2.5 billion≤total assets<\$3 billion	\$15million	between 33% and 35%
16	\$3 billion≤total assets<\$4 billion	\$16 million	between 33% and 35%
17	\$4 billion≤total assets<\$5 billion	\$17 million	between 33% and 35%
18	\$5 billion≤total assets<\$6 billion	\$18million	between 33% and 35%
19	\$6 billion≤total assets<\$7 billion	\$19 million	between 33% and 35%
20	\$7 billion≤total assets<\$8 billion	\$20million	between 33% and 35%
21	\$9 billion≤total assets<\$10 billion	\$21million	between 33% and 35%
22	\$10 billion≤total assets<\$15 billion	\$22 million	between 35% and 36%
23	\$15 billion≤total assets<\$20 billion	\$23 million	between 35% and 36%
24	\$20 billion≤total assets<\$25 billion	\$24million	between 35% and 36%
25	\$25billion≤total assets<\$30 billion	\$25 million	between 35% and 36%
26	\$30 billion≤total assets<\$35 billion	\$26 million	between 35% and 36%
27	\$35 billion≤total assets<\$40 billion	\$27 million	between 35% and 36%
28	\$40 billion≤total assets<\$45 billion	\$28million	between 36% and 38%
29	\$45 billion≤total assets<\$50 billion	\$29 million	between 36% and 38%
30	\$50 billion≤total assets<\$55 billion	\$30 million	between 36% and 38%
31	\$55 billion≤total assets<\$60 billion	\$31million	between 36% and 38%
32	\$60 billion≤total assets<\$65 billion	\$32 million	between 36% and 38%
33	\$65 billion≤total assets<\$70 billion	\$33 million	between 36% and 38%

34	\$70 billion ≤ total assets < \$75 billion	\$34million	between 36% and 38%
35	\$75 billion ≤ total assets < \$80 billion	\$35million	between 36% and 38%
36	\$80 billion ≤ total assets < \$85 billion	\$36million	between 36% and 38%
37	\$85 billion ≤ total assets < \$90 billion	\$37 million	between 36% and 38%
38	\$90 billion ≤ total assets < \$95 billion	\$38million	between 36% and 38%
39	\$95 billion ≤ total assets < \$1 trillion	\$39 million	between 36% and 38%
40	\$1 trillion ≤ total assets	\$40million	between 37% and 40%

4. Charitable or trust funds should not be used as tax-avoidance tools

Charitable funds or trust funds cannot be used for tax avoidance. Governments must act promptly to address this issue. The purpose of charitable foundations is to serve society and support those in need. Governments should ensure that these funds are used for public welfare, like education and healthcare, to promote fairness and justice. However, some wealthy individuals misuse these foundations to evade taxes by transferring large amounts of wealth into them. This undermines public trust and unfairly burdens society. Governments and the United Nations should establish a consensus requiring funds to benefit vulnerable groups or specific projects within a specific timeframe. Reasonable tax policies must be implemented to prevent misuse. Governments should establish a strong tax framework, discouraging tax evasion, and encouraging genuine philanthropy. Governments and the United Nations should establish a governmental consensus, requiring that any funds or assets entering charitable foundations be fully and completely used for aiding vulnerable groups or specific projects within 5-6 years. Ethical principles should guide governments' actions, while regulatory oversight should ensure transparent and responsible philanthropic endeavors.

5. Government consensus on global collection of income tax, renunciation tax, inheritance tax or gift tax, charitable and trust funds, and world peace

The author proposes that all United Nations Member States or regional organizations engage in discussions and reach a consensus on the global establishment and collection of inheritance taxes, etc. This consensus should be emphasized through a government declaration. Implementing similar tax rates for major taxes, such as inheritance tax, renunciation tax, and personal income tax on a global scale under UN leadership can prevent countries without indigenous wealth creation from becoming tax havens for the wealthy. This would help address poverty disparities, potential instability, and the threat to global peace caused by the concentration of private wealth. Swift implementation, along with new tax laws in different countries, can assist the United States in managing its debt crisis and promote social responsibility among the wealthy. However, countries with high tax rates that have not faced a debt crisis may temporarily abstain from participating. The suggested tax rates in the tables provided cater more

toward developed countries but can be adjusted for others (Table 2, Table 3.). Additionally, the author calls for an increase in Japan's minimum inheritance tax threshold from the current 30 million yen to 90 million yen to protect individuals' survival rights and align with universal values¹⁷. This tax system reform can enhance the economy, reduce debt, bridge the wealth gap, and facilitate currency circulation. It is a significant measure for implementing behavioral economics principles and assessing government ethics.

The tax system in this study can do a better job than the first tax system reform related to inheritance tax, gift tax, renunciation tax and personal income tax designed by the author of this article in terms of promoting the reduction of the number of the world's super-rich, narrowing the gap between the rich and poor, reducing wars and maintaining world peace¹⁸. A global governmental consensus or a United Nations declaration on the above-mentioned tax system is essential for achieving lasting world peace. Only when the United Nations plays a leading role, mainstream media shape public opinion responsibly and the constitutions of various countries are amended simultaneously can the above-mentioned tax system be effectively implemented jointly and rational global governance be effectively achieved.

The author firmly believes that once this new tax system can achieve global reform, it can be regarded as a revolutionary change and a major innovation in reducing wars from the perspective of war behavior economics or military behavior economics, and it will bring a new milestone-like future for maintaining global peace and sustainable development.

Tax system reforms will inevitably trigger fierce disputes, resistance or conflict. Whether they can be implemented is related to the religions, beliefs, philosophies and cultures of the dominant countries. A country's civilization, religion, philosophical ideas and culture determine its future. **The civilizations of ancient Egypt, ancient Greece and Sumer were all forged by Western missionaries. 5,000 years ago, the Sumerian region was still submerged in sea water. How could it possibly have the earliest civilization in the world?** The only civilization in the world is the Chinese civilization, which has lasted for at least 10,000 years. Western Catholicism, Christianity, Judaism, and the Bible can all be proved by mathematical methods that emerged after the 15th century. Most of the Bible's content was created based on Chinese culture and beliefs. If you are familiar with the Chinese language, you may well know that some parts were even written by Chinese people, and even the name "Christ" was first created in China.

If the invisible super-rich around the world and the officials who control the political arena do not want to face a situation in the future where their entire families are killed due to the huge gap between the rich and poor, just like what happened during the Huang Chao Uprising, they should not block the revolutionary reforms of this new tax system.

If you want to check whether the core values of Western religions are correct, Tesla's sensing system, which uses the integration of cameras and millimeter-wave radars for detection, can detect the souls of the deceased in cemeteries¹⁹, indicating that there are serious flaws in the religions and philosophies that guide people's lives in the Western world today. Only traditional Chinese philosophy is reasonable. If you don't

believe it, you might as well drive to a cemetery with your friends at night, and it will only take half an hour to test whether the religions and philosophies that guide people's lives in the West are correct or not.

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